

PREPARATION OF SOME MONOCYANOETHYLATED KETONES

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The ketonic hydrolysis of an ethyl α -alkyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl)acetoacetate results in the formation of an α -(2-cyanoethyl)ketone.

Ketones, which have a methinyl, methylene or methyl group contiguous to the carbonyl group, react with acrylonitrile with the formation of a mono-, di-, tri- or even a poly-cyanoethylation product. Thus, acetone reacts with acrylonitrile to yield a small quantity of a monocyanoethylation product $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$, but the reaction mainly gives the tricyanoethylation product $\text{CH}_3\text{CO}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN})_3$ (Bruson and Riener, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2850). An unsymmetrical aliphatic ketone, like methylethyl ketone, on the other hand, reacts with acrylonitrile under appropriate conditions to yield a product where the methylene group has been dicyanoethylated in preference to a methyl group (Bruson and Riener, *loc. cit.*). It will be observed that in the above cases, the reaction with acrylonitrile does not stop at the stage of monocyanoethylation.

The reaction between acrylonitrile and monoalkylated acetoacetic esters (Misra and Shukla, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 455) has now been utilised to furnish a general route for the synthesis of the α -(2-cyanoethyl)ketones. In this method the resulting α -alkyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl) acetoacetate is submitted to *ketonic hydrolysis* to furnish the α -(2-cyanoethyl)ketone, thus :

It was found that when the cyanoethylation product (II) was heated with 5% potassium hydroxide, the *ketonic hydrolysis* had not taken place to any appreciable extent. When, however, the product (II) was heated with 10% potassium hydroxide for about five hours, extraction of the resulting mixture with ethylene dichloride and evaporation of the ethylene dichloride extract furnished the desired monocyanoethylated ketone. The yields of the ketones were 30.6 to 43.4% only.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Ethyl- α -Alkyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl)acetoacetates.—These compounds were prepared in accordance with the method already described (Misra and Shukla, *loc. cit.*).

Preparation of Monocyanoethylated Ketones: 3-(β -Cyanoethyl)-2-butanone.—Ethyl α -methyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl)acetoacetate (11 g.) was heated on a waterbath with 10% potassium hydroxide (50 c. c.) for five hours. The mixture was cooled and

extracted with ethylene dichloride several times. The ethylene dichloride layer was washed several times with water till it ceased to react alkaline to litmus paper. It was then allowed to stand over anhydrous magnesium sulphate overnight, and the ethylene dichloride evaporated off under reduced pressure. The residual oil was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction of b. p. 93°/8 mm. was collected, yield 2.4 g. (34.4%). (Found : N, 10.8. $C_7H_{11}ON$ requires N, 11.2 per cent.).

The other monocynoethylated ketones have been prepared similarly. They are described in Table I.

TABLE I

** R =	Monocynoethylated ketone formed.	Yield.	B. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen	
					Calc.	Found.
Methyl	3-(β -C*)-2-butanone	34.4%	93/8 mm.	$C_7H_{11}ON$	10.8	11.2
Ethyl	3-(β -C)-2-pentanone	43.4	114/12	$C_8H_{13}ON$	9.5	10.07
n-Propyl	3-(β -C)-2-hexanone	36.2	110/5-6	$C_9H_{15}ON$	8.4	9.15
n-Butyl	3-(β -C)-2-heptanone	34.8	117/6-7	$C_{10}H_{17}ON$	8.0	8.38
n-Amyl	3-(β -C)-2-octanone	31.9	120/8	$C_{11}H_{19}ON$	7.2	7.7
Benzyl	3-(β -C)-4-phenyl- -2-butanone	30.6	95/5	$C_{13}H_{17}ON$	6.8	6.96

*C-denotes cyanoethyl.

**R = α -alkyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl) acetoacetate.

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